
DMP du projet "The Lund Jet Plane for Precision Physics"

Plan de gestion de données créé à l'aide de DMP OPIDoR, basé sur le modèle "Science Europe : modèle structuré" fourni par Science Europe.

Renseignements sur le plan

Titre du plan	DMP du projet "The Lund Jet Plane for Precision Physics"
Version	Version initiale
Domaines de recherche (selon classification de l'OCDE)	Physical sciences
Langue	eng
Date de création	2023-01-27
Date de dernière modification	2023-02-12
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Renseignements sur le projet

Titre du projet	The Lund Jet Plane for Precision Physics
Acronyme	LEAP-physics
Résumé	<i>Les progrès récents dans la physique des jets aux collisionneurs hadroniques ont démontré qu'une compréhension théorique approfondie des structures inhérentes à ces objets, associée aux possibilités expérimentales de disséquer, mesurer et utiliser cette information, conduisent à un accroissement spectaculaire du potentiel de découverte de nouvelle physique. L'idée de cartographier l'espace de phase au sein d'un jet unique en utilisant le plan de jet de Lund représente une avancée théorique majeure. Les propriétés analytiques de cette approche de la structure d'un jet, associées à la possibilité d'effectuer des mesures précises du plan de jet de Lund à l'aide du détecteur ATLAS auprès du Grand Collisionneur Hadronique (LHC), ainsi que via les études de prospective auprès des collisionneurs futurs (FCC-ee), fournissent un éclairage unique sur la Chromodynamique Quantique, ainsi que sur la physique potentielle au-delà du Modèle Standard.</i>

Sources de financement

- Agence Nationale de la Recherche : ANR-21-CE31-0012

Date de début 2022-03-01

Date de fin 2025-09-30

Partenaires

- Laboratoire physique nucléaire et hautes énergies (199712631X)

Produits de recherche :

1. ATLAS jet uncertainty package (Logiciel)
2. ATLAS jet tagger tool (Logiciel)

3. HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions (Jeu de données)
4. Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation (Autre)
5. Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee (Texte)
6. Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals (Texte)
7. ATLAS internal documentation (Texte)

Contributeurs

Nom	Affiliation	Rôles
ATLAS collaboration		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsable de la production ou de la collecte des données (Uncertainty package, Extracted alpha_S, Unfolded Measurement, Tagger tool, Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable juridique (Tagger tool, Uncertainty package, Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents)
CAMACHO TORO Reina - https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9192-8028	LPNHE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personne contact pour les données (Uncertainty package, Tagger tool) • Responsable de la conservation à long terme des données (Tagger tool, Uncertainty package) • Responsable de la documentation des données (Tagger tool, Uncertainty package) • Responsable de la qualité des données (Tagger tool, Uncertainty package) • Responsable du dépôt et de la diffusion des données (Tagger tool, Uncertainty package) • Responsable du stockage des données (Uncertainty package, Tagger tool) • Responsable du traitement et de l'analyse des données (Uncertainty package, Tagger tool)
FCC-ee Monte Carlo simulation group		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsable de la conservation à long terme des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable de la production ou de la collecte des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable du dépôt et de la diffusion des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable juridique (Document FCC-ee perf)

Nom	Affiliation	Rôles
MALAESCU Bogdan - https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8813-3830	LPNHE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinateur du projet • Personne contact pour les données (Internal documents, Scientific articles, Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S) • Responsable de la conservation à long terme des données (Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents, Unfolded Measurement) • Responsable de la documentation des données (Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable de la production ou de la collecte des données (Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable de la qualité des données (Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable des questions éthiques (Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable du dépôt et de la diffusion des données (Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents, Unfolded Measurement) • Responsable du plan de gestion de données • Responsable du stockage des données (Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents) • Responsable du traitement et de l'analyse des données (Unfolded Measurement, Extracted alpha_S, Scientific articles, Internal documents)
Poggioli Luc - https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3210-6646	LPNHE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personne contact pour les données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable de la conservation à long terme des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable de la documentation des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable de la production ou de la collecte des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable de la qualité des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable du dépôt et de la diffusion des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable du stockage des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable du traitement et de l'analyse des données (Document FCC-ee perf) • Responsable juridique (Document FCC-ee perf)

DMP du projet "The Lund Jet Plane for Precision Physics"

1. Description des données et collecte ou réutilisation de données existantes

ATLAS jet uncertainty package

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	ATLAS jet uncertainty package
Description	Software package allowing to propagate the uncertainties related to the jet energy calibration and to the jet substructure. This package will be used in a large number of ATLAS physics analyses.
Type	Logiciel
Workpackage	WP1
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification	The first calibration studies are being performed using data collected during the Run 2 of the LHC, together with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulations.
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1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode	Proton-proton collisions
Description	In addition to the already existing data, we will use data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.
Nature des données	Données expérimentales
Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ATLAS : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS• LHC : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC

ATLAS jet tagger tool

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	ATLAS jet tagger tool
Description	Software package allowing to tag boson jets vs quark/gluon jets, as well as quarks vs gluons. This package will be used in a large number of ATLAS physics analyses.
Type	Logiciel
Workpackage	WP3
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification The first studies will be performed using data collected at the beginning of the Run 3 of the LHC, together with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulations.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode Proton-proton collisions

Description In addition to the already existing data, we will use data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.

Nature des données Données expérimentales

Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés

- ATLAS : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS>
- LHC : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC>

HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions
Description	The main research product is a multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, together with its uncertainties and the corresponding correlations between different phase-space regions. This experimental result will be made public through the HepData repository (http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/). The theoretical predictions for this observable are computationally intensive and will also be made public in the same HepData entry.
Type	Jeu de données
Workpackage	WP2
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification The first studies will be performed using data collected during the Run 2 and at the beginning of the Run 3 of the LHC, together with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulations.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode Proton-proton collisions

Description In addition to the already existing data, we will use data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.

Nature des données Données expérimentales

Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés

- ATLAS : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS>
- LHC : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC>

Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation
Description	The value of the strong coupling constant (α_S), together with its uncertainty, will be extracted through a fit of the experimental measurement of the Lund Jet Plane. The resulting value of α_S , together with its uncertainty, will be made public in a paper, on arXiv (https://arxiv.org/) and in a peer-reviewed journal. The determination of α_S at different energies will be used to perform a test of the renormalisation group equation predicted by QCD, the result of which will be described in the same paper.
Type	Autre
Workpackage	WP2
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification The first studies will be performed using (the unfolded measurement based on) data collected during the Run 2 and at the beginning of the Run 3 of the LHC, together with the corresponding theoretical predictions.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode Proton-proton collisions

Description In addition to the already existing data, we will use (the unfolded measurement based on) data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.

Nature des données Données expérimentales

Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés

- ATLAS : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS>
- LHC : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC>

Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee
Description	Document summarising the outcome of studies exploring the performance of various types of detectors for FCC-ee, in the context of the reconstruction of the Lund Jet Plane. These studies will be based on simulated event samples that will also be available for other people doing performance studies for FCC-ee.
Type	Texte
Workpackage	WP1
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification This document will describe studies based in part on existing samples of simulated events for the FCC-ee.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode Full/fast simulation

Description If available, we will use fully simulated samples, with a precise description of the detector topology, for e⁺e⁻ collision events with jets in the final state. Alternatively, we will use fast (still accurate) simulations for the same types of events and detectors.

Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés

- FCC-ee MC production :

Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals

1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche

Nom	Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals
Description	The physics and performance studies performed in this project will be described in scientific articles made public on arXiv (https://arxiv.org/) and published in peer-reviewed journals.
Type	Texte
Workpackage	WP1, WP2, WP3
Mots clés (texte libre)	
Contient des données personnelles ?	Non
Contient des données sensibles ?	Non
Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?	Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?

Justification

The scientific articles will describe studies using data collected during the Run 2 and/or at the beginning of the Run 3 of the LHC, together with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulations.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?**Titre de la méthode**

Proton-proton collisions

Description

In addition to the already existing data, we will use data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.

Nature des données

Données expérimentales

Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés

- ATLAS : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS>
- LHC : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC>

ATLAS internal documentation**1.1 Description générale du produit de recherche****Nom**

ATLAS internal documentation

Description

The physics and performance studies performed in this project using ATLAS data will be described into detail in ATLAS internal documents.

Type

Texte

Workpackage

WP1, WP2, WP3

Mots clés (texte libre)**Contient des données personnelles ?**

Non

Contient des données sensibles ?

Non

Prend en compte des aspects éthiques ?

Non

1.2 Est-ce que des données existantes seront réutilisées ?**Justification**

The ATLAS internal documentation will describe studies using data collected during the Run 2 and/or at the beginning of the Run 3 of the LHC, together with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulations.

1.3 Comment seront produites/collectées les nouvelles données ?

Titre de la méthode	Proton-proton collisions
Description	In addition to the already existing data, we will use data collected with the ATLAS detector during the ongoing Run 3 of the LHC, with the corresponding Monte-Carlo simulated events.
Nature des données	Données expérimentales
Equipements, plateaux techniques utilisés	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATLAS : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/ATLAS • LHC : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/LHC

2. Documentation et qualité des données

ATLAS jet uncertainty package	
2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?	
Description	<p>We will use data in the ATLAS DAOD format, see e.g. https://inspirehep.net/files/b55bb370a567b00c6995f70688480962 https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/AtlasPublic/ComputingandSoftwarePublicResults</p> <p>The package itself will be made available to the collaboration through GitLab (https://gitlab.cern.ch/).</p>
2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?	
Description	<p>Data quality checks (see e.g. https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.04632) with both online and offline monitoring; and internal review of the performance studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.</p> <p>In addition, a code reviewing process is in place in ATLAS, involving the versioning for our code and CI steps implemented for most of our tools. The ATLAS Athena reconstruction code is also publicly available (see https://gitlab.cern.ch/atlas/athena ; https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/athena/athena-intro/).</p>

ATLAS jet tagger tool	
2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?	
Description	<p>We will use data in the ATLAS DAOD format, see e.g. https://inspirehep.net/files/b55bb370a567b00c6995f70688480962 https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/AtlasPublic/ComputingandSoftwarePublicResults</p> <p>The package itself will be made available to the collaboration through GitLab (https://gitlab.cern.ch/).</p>
2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?	

Description	<p>Data quality checks (see e.g. https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.04632) with both online and offline monitoring; and internal review of the performance studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.</p> <p>In addition, a code reviewing process is in place in ATLAS, involving the versioning for our code and CI steps implemented for most of our tools. The ATLAS Athena reconstruction code is also publicly available (see https://gitlab.cern.ch/atlas/athena ; https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/athena/athena-intro/).</p>
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HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions	
2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?	
Description	<p>We will use data in the ATLAS DAOD format, see e.g. https://inspirehep.net/files/b55bb370a567b00c6995f70688480962 https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/AtlasPublic/ComputingandSoftwarePublicResults</p> <p>The measurement itself will be made public through the HepData repository (http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/).</p>
2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?	
Description	<p>Cross-checks of the various analysis steps whenever possible; data quality checks (see e.g. https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.04632) with both online and offline monitoring; and internal review of the analysis studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.</p> <p>In addition, a code reviewing process is in place in ATLAS, involving the versioning for our code and CI steps implemented for most of our tools. The ATLAS Athena reconstruction code is also publicly available (see https://gitlab.cern.ch/atlas/athena ; https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/athena/athena-intro/).</p>

Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation	
2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?	
Description	<p>The fit to extract α_S will use as input the data on the unfolded measurement, in the format used for the HepData repository (http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/). The result of the fit itself will be reported in the published article.</p>
2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?	
Description	<p>Cross-checks of the various analysis steps whenever possible and internal review of the analysis studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.</p>

Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee	
2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?	
Description	<p>We will use simulated samples in the Root format.</p>

2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?

Description

Cross-checks of the various analysis steps whenever possible and review by other scientists working on FCC-ee performance studies.

Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals

2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?

Description

The results of the studies will be reported in the scientific article itself and in the associated HepData repository (<http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/>).

2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?

Description

Cross-checks of the various analysis steps whenever possible and internal review of the analysis studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.

ATLAS internal documentation

2.1 Quelles métadonnées et quelle documentation (par exemple mode d'organisation des données) accompagneront les données ?

Description

The results of the studies will be reported in the internal documents themselves and in the associated HepData repository draft.

2.2 Quelles seront les méthodes utilisées pour assurer la qualité scientifique des données ?

Description

Cross-checks of the various analysis steps whenever possible and internal review of the analysis studies performed by the ATLAS collaboration.

3. Exigences légales et éthiques, code de conduite

ATLAS jet uncertainty package

3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?

Description

Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.

3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?

Description

All the information about the studies, the input and output data will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.

3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?

Description

Not applicable: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data.

ATLAS jet tagger tool

3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?

Description

Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.

3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?

Description

All the information about the studies, the input and output data will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.

3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?

Description

Not applicable: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data.

HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions

3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?

Description

Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.

3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?

Description	All the information about the studies, the input and output data will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.
3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?	
Description	Not applicable: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data.
Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation	
3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?	
Description	Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.
3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?	
Description	All the information about the studies, the input and output results will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.
3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?	
Description	Not applicable: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data.
Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee	
3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?	
Description	Not applicable: using simulated data.
3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?	
Description	All the information about the studies and their results will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the review by the scientists involved in the FCC-ee studies, in the the relevant working groups.
3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?	

Description	Not applicable: using simulated data for FCC-ee and the corresponding detector designs.
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Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals	
3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?	
Description	Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.
3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?	
Description	All the information about the studies and their results will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.
3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?	
Description	Not applicable for what concerns the data taking itself: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data. The contributions of analysers for each work/paper/internal documental is recognized. We include the information on the individual contributions in a database accessible to all ATLAS members.

ATLAS internal documentation	
3.1 Quelles seront les mesures appliquées pour assurer la protection des données à caractère personnel ?	
Description	Not applicable: using experimental and simulated data.
3.2 Quelles sont les contraintes juridiques (sensibilité des données autres qu'à caractère personnel, confidentialité, ...) à prendre en compte pour le partage et le stockage des données ?	
Description	All the information about the studies and their results will be kept private, on computers with restricted access at CERN and/or at LPNHE. Part of this information will only be made public after the full review and approval by the ATLAS collaboration.
3.3 Quels sont les aspects éthiques à prendre en compte lors de la collecte des données ?	
Description	Not applicable for what concerns the data taking itself: using ATLAS experimental and simulated data. The contributions of analysers for each work/paper/internal documental is recognized. We include the information on the individual contributions in a database accessible to all ATLAS members.

4. Traitement et analyse des données

ATLAS jet uncertainty package

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The data analysis steps involving running over large event samples will be performed using the ATLAS grid infrastructure and the CONDOR batch system at CERN.

<https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/>

<https://batchdocs.web.cern.ch/>

ATLAS jet tagger tool

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The data analysis steps involving running over large event samples will be performed using the ATLAS grid infrastructure and the CONDOR batch system at CERN.

<https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/>

<https://batchdocs.web.cern.ch/>

HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The data analysis steps involving running over large event samples will be performed using the ATLAS grid infrastructure and the CONDOR batch system at CERN. Certain steps that are less CPU and I/O intensive will be performed on the lxplus system at CERN.

<https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/>

<https://batchdocs.web.cern.ch/>

https://abpcomputing.web.cern.ch/computing_resources/lxplus/

Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The fits for the extraction of α_S will be performed on the lxplus system at CERN.

https://abpcomputing.web.cern.ch/computing_resources/lxplus/

Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The studies for the performance of the FCC-ee detector models will be performed on the CONDOR and lxplus systems at CERN.

<https://batchdocs.web.cern.ch/>

https://abpcomputing.web.cern.ch/computing_resources/lxplus/

Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The editing of the scientific articles will be performed on the lxplus system at CERN. The corresponding information will be saved and shared among the editors using GitLab.

https://abpcomputing.web.cern.ch/computing_resources/lxplus/

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/>

ATLAS internal documentation

4.1 Comment et avec quels moyens seront traitées les données ?

Description

The editing of the internal ATLAS documentation will be performed on the lxplus system at CERN. The corresponding information will be saved and shared among the editors using GitLab.

https://abpcomputing.web.cern.ch/computing_resources/lxplus/

<https://gitlab.cern.ch/>

5. Stockage et sauvegarde des données pendant le processus de recherche

ATLAS jet uncertainty package

5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?

Besoins de stockage	<p>The large (i.e. of several To) samples of data and Monte-Carlo events (DAODs) used to derive the inputs of the package are stored on the ATLAS computing grid. Copies of these samples are saved at several sites. In case some of these samples are lost, they can be produced again from the raw data files, which also have backups on tapes.</p> <p>The access to these data is protected through a system of grid certificates, such that only authorised persons can read the data.</p> <p>Smaller data files (i.e. of about 1Go or less), containing histograms with correction factors and uncertainties, will be stored on the EOS system at CERN and in GitLab. Here also, automatic backups are being done and the access is restricted to authorised persons only.</p> <p>https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/ https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/</p>
Volume estimé des données	5
Unité	To
Equipements, plateaux techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GRIF : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/GRIF
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through Grid Certification and/or through list of authorised accounts for data stored on EOS at CERN.

ATLAS jet tagger tool	
5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?	
Besoins de stockage	<p>The large (i.e. of several To) samples of data and Monte-Carlo events (DAODs) used to derive the inputs of the package are stored on the ATLAS computing grid. Copies of these samples are saved at several sites. In case some of these samples are lost, they can be produced again from the raw data files, which also have backups on tapes.</p> <p>The access to these data is protected through a system of grid certificates, such that only authorised persons can read the data.</p> <p>Smaller data files (i.e. of about 1Go or less), containing histograms with correction factors and uncertainties, will be stored on the EOS system at CERN and in GitLab. Here also, automatic backups are being done and the access is restricted to authorised persons only.</p> <p>https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/ https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/</p>
Volume estimé des données	5
Unité	To
Equipements, plateaux techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GRIF : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/GRIF
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through Grid Certification and/or through list of authorised accounts for data stored on EOS at CERN.

HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions	
5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?	

Besoins de stockage	<p>The large (i.e. of several To) samples of data and Monte-Carlo events (DAODs) used to perform the measurement are stored on the ATLAS computing grid. Copies of these samples are saved at several sites. In case some of these samples are lost, they can be produced again from the raw data files, which also have backups on tapes.</p> <p>The access to these data is protected through a system of grid certificates, such that only authorised persons can read the data.</p> <p>Smaller data files (i.e. of about 1Go or less), containing histograms for the measured distributions and their uncertainties, will be stored on the EOS system at CERN and in GitLab. Here also, automatic backups are being done and the access is restricted to authorised persons only.</p> <p>https://atlassoftwaredocs.web.cern.ch/gridtutorial/ https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/</p>
Volume estimé des données	5
Unité	To
Equipements, plateaux techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GRIF : https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/GRIF
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through Grid Certification and/or through list of authorised accounts for data stored on EOS at CERN.

Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation	
5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?	
Besoins de stockage	<p>The outcome of the α_S extraction (i.e. plots and the α_S value itself) will be stored in the internal documentation and in the scientific paper, saved in GitLab at CERN.</p> <p>https://gitlab.cern.ch/</p>
Volume estimé des données	100
Unité	Mo
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access to GitLab entries at CERN restricted through list of authorised accounts.

Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee	
5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?	
Besoins de stockage	<p>The samples of Monte-Carlo events used to perform the studies will be stored on the EOS system at CERN, as well as at the IN2P3 computing center in Lyon (https://cc.in2p3.fr/). The documents summarising the outcome of the studies will be stored in GitLab at CERN. Automatic backups are being done and the access is restricted to authorised persons only.</p> <p>https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://eos-web.web.cern.ch/eos-web/</p>
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	To
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through list of authorised accounts for data stored on EOS and on GitLab at CERN.

Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals

5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?

Besoins de stockage	The drafts of the scientific papers will be stored in GitLab and in the CDS system at CERN. https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://cdsweb.cern.ch/?ln=fr
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	Go
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through list of authorised accounts for the files stored on GitLab at CERN.

ATLAS internal documentation

5.1 Comment les données seront-elles stockées et sauvegardées tout au long du projet ?

Besoins de stockage	The drafts of the internal documentation (i.e. supporting documents) will be stored in GitLab and in the CDS system at CERN. https://gitlab.cern.ch/ https://cdsweb.cern.ch/?ln=fr
Volume estimé des données	5
Unité	Go
Mesures prises pour la sécurité des données	Access restricted through list of authorised accounts for the files stored on GitLab at CERN.

6. Partage des données et conservation à long terme

ATLAS jet uncertainty package

6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?

Modalités de partage	The jet uncertainty package and its inputs files will be shared with the members of the ATLAS collaboration through the GitLab repository. All analyses will be performed using code versioned within a commonly accessible GitLab repository, with the code review used to ensure that all commits by one team member are checked by at least one other team member and properly documented. The code will be available for other members of the ATLAS collaboration. ATLAS is committed to preserving all the information required to support the use of reconstructed data throughout the lifetime of the collaboration, which also means that the option to make it open access is preserved to be released approximately five years after collection (CERN Open Data portal: http://opendata.cern.ch and CERN Open Data Policy for the LHC Experiments at http://opendata.cern.ch/docs/cern-open-data-policy-for-lhc-experiments). The fact of using code versioned means that all analyses within this project can be made available under Open Access too at that point, without any further work having to be done.
Potentiel de réutilisation	Package useful for numerous ATLAS physics analyses.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?

Justification	The jet uncertainty package and its inputs files will be useful for physics analyses that may be performed at a later time within the ATLAS collaboration or by external researchers using open data.
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	Go
Archive	:

ATLAS jet tagger tool	
6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?	
Modalités de partage	<p>The tagger tool and its inputs files will be shared with the members of the ATLAS collaboration through the GitLab repository.</p> <p>All analyses will be performed using code versioned within a commonly accessible GitLab repository, with the code review used to ensure that all commits by one team member are checked by at least one other team member and properly documented. The code will be available for other members of the ATLAS collaboration. ATLAS is committed to preserving all the information required to support the use of reconstructed data throughout the lifetime of the collaboration, which also means that the option to make it open access is preserved to be released approximately five years after collection (CERN Open Data portal: http://opendata.cern.ch and CERN Open Data Policy for the LHC Experiments at http://opendata.cern.ch/docs/cern-open-data-policy-for-lhc-experiments). The fact of using code versioned means that all analyses within this project can be made available under Open Access too at that point, without any further work having to be done.</p>
Potentiel de réutilisation	Tool useful for numerous ATLAS physics analyses.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?	
Justification	The tagger tool and its inputs files will be useful for physics analyses that may be performed at a later time within the ATLAS collaboration or by external researchers using open data.
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	Go
Archive	:

HepData entry for multi-differential unfolded measurement of the Lund Jet Plane, as well as for its theoretical predictions	
6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?	

Modalités de partage

Information on the experimental results (such as tables, figures, breakdown of systematic uncertainties or any supplementary information for result reproducibility) will be made available in a digital format to the HepData repository (<http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/>) for preservation and sharing purposes with no financial costs and no access restrictions.

All analyses will be performed using code versioned within a commonly accessible GitLab repository, with the code review used to ensure that all commits by one team member are checked by at least one other team member and properly documented. The code will be available for other members of the ATLAS collaboration. ATLAS is committed to preserving all the information required to support the use of reconstructed data throughout the lifetime of the collaboration, which also means that the option to make it open access is preserved to be released approximately five years after collection (CERN Open Data portal: <http://opendata.cern.ch> and CERN Open Data Policy for the LHC Experiments at <http://opendata.cern.ch/docs/cern-open-data-policy-for-lhc-experiments>). The fact of using code versioned means that all analyses within this project can be made available under Open Access too at that point, without any further work having to be done.

Potentiel de réutilisation

The information uploaded to HepData can be used for global fits of Parton Distribution Functions and/or α_S , as well as for constraining models of New Physics beyond the Standard Model.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?**Justification**

The long term storage of the results of these measurements (information uploaded to HepData) is useful as it can be used for global fits of Parton Distribution Functions and/or α_S , as well as for constraining models of New Physics beyond the Standard Model.

Volume estimé des données

1

Unité

Go

Archive

:

Extracted value of the strong coupling constant and test of the renormalisation group equation**6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?****Modalités de partage**

The extracted α_S values will be shared through the published scientific articles and through HepData entries.

All analyses will be performed using code versioned within a commonly accessible GitLab repository, with the code review used to ensure that all commits by one team member are checked by at least one other team member and properly documented. The code will be available for other members of the ATLAS collaboration. ATLAS is committed to preserving all the information required to support the use of reconstructed data throughout the lifetime of the collaboration, which also means that the option to make it open access is preserved to be released approximately five years after collection (CERN Open Data portal: <http://opendata.cern.ch> and CERN Open Data Policy for the LHC Experiments at <http://opendata.cern.ch/docs/cern-open-data-policy-for-lhc-experiments>). The fact of using code versioned means that all analyses within this project can be made available under Open Access too at that point, without any further work having to be done.

Potentiel de réutilisation

The extracted α_S values will be included in reviews like e.g. the one done by PDG.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?

Justification	The extracted alpha_S values will be preserved through the published scientific articles and through HepData entries.
Volume estimé des données	10
Unité	Mo
Archive	:

Document to be used as input to detector design for FCC-ee

6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?

Modalités de partage	The raw data used for these studies will be shared with the other researchers performing studies on FCC-ee, through shared EOS directories at CERN. All analyses will be performed using code versioned within a commonly accessible GitLab repository, with the code review used to ensure that all commits by one team member are checked by at least one other team member and properly documented.
Potentiel de réutilisation	The simulated samples, methods and software developed here can be used in other performance studies for FCC-ee.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?

Justification	The simulated samples for the FCC-ee studies need to be preserved on the timescale of a few years, until more refined models of the corresponding detectors are designed and the corresponding simulated samples are produced.
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	To
Archive	:

Scientific articles made public on arXiv and published in peer-reviewed journals

6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?

Modalités de partage	Results will be published in highly-ranked open-access peer-reviewed scientific journals and simultaneously in the arXiv (https://arxiv.org/) database. Any additional information on the experimental results (such as tables, figures, breakdown of systematic uncertainties or any supplementary information for result reproducibility) will be made available in a digital format to the HepData repository (http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/) for preservation and sharing purposes with no financial costs and no access restrictions.
Potentiel de réutilisation	The approaches described in these articles can be used for future studies by ATLAS and/or by other experiments. The information uploaded to HepData can be used for global fits of Parton Distribution Functions and/or alpha_S, as well as for constraining models of New Physics beyond the Standard Model.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?

Justification	The methods employed here will be useful for future analyses, while the information uploaded to HepData will be useful for re-interpretation studies.
Volume estimé des données	1
Unité	Go
Archive	:

ATLAS internal documentation

6.1 Comment les données seront-elles partagées ?

Modalités de partage	The supporting material (internal documents) will be stored in GitLab and in the CDS system at CERN. The access to this material is restricted to the members of the ATLAS collaboration.
Potentiel de réutilisation	The approaches described in this documentation can be used for future ATLAS analyses.

6.2 Comment les données seront-elles conservées à long terme ?

Justification	The methods employed here will be useful for future ATLAS analyses.
Volume estimé des données	5
Unité	Go
Archive	: